

Supplementary Fig. S10 The gain of chromosomal segment in $DH_{1:2}$ progenies. The $DH_{0:1}$ plants StanleyLandmarkDH02009-0, StanleyLandmarkDH01058-0, and StanleyLandmarkDH01063-0 derived from selfing of the respective primary DH lines were selfed to produce seven, seven, and five $DH_{1:2}$ progenies respectively. **A)** A homozygous deletion on the short arm of chromosome 4D was observed in StanleyLandmarkDH2009-0. The $DH_{1:2}$ progenies had normal (DH2009-0-5) and hemizygous deletion (DH02009-0-1, DH02009-0-2, DH02009-0-3, DH02009-0-4, DH02009-0-6, and DH02009-0-7). **B)** A homozygous deletion on the short arm of chromosome 3B was observed in StanleyLandmarkDH01058-0. The $DH_{1:2}$ progenies had hemizygous (DH01058-0-1, DH01058-0-4, DH01058-0-6, and DH01058-0-7) and homozygous (DH01058-0-2, DH01058-0-5, and DH01058-0-10) deletion. **C)** A homozygous deletion on the long arm of chromosome 2B was observed in StanleyLandmarkDH01063-0. The $DH_{1:2}$ progenies had normal (DH01063-0-2, DH01063-0-3, and DH01063-0-5) and homozygous deletion (DH01063-0-1 and DH01063-0-4). Each panel shows the genomic position of a given chromosome in 1Mb bins on the physical map of the CDC Landmark reference genome in the x-axis with points showing the normalized number of reads mapping to the respective bin. The vertical axis shows both normalized read count (left) and chromosome dosage (right). The parental allele for individual SNP variants is shown on top for CDC Landmark (red) and CDC Stanley (blue) alleles. Centromere positions are showing as black triangle.